

SODIUM 2 : 6-DICHLOROINDOPHENOLATE

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2 : 6-Dichloro-4-aminophenol, obtained in quantitative yield by alkaline hydrosulphite reduction of the corresponding nitrophenol, has been condensed with phenol in presence of sodium hypochlorite to form the sodium 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol dye in high yield, obviating the isolation of the intermediate 2 : 6-dichloroquinone chlorimide.

The sodium salt of 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol is a redox indicator used specifically in the determination of vitamin-C in biological materials. The deep blue aqueous solution of the dye (I) is quantitatively reduced to its leuco base (II), ascorbic acid itself being oxidised to dehydroascorbic acid.

In the course of investigations on the biosynthesis of vitamin-C in plants (Panse and Sreenivasan, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 303) difficulty was experienced in obtaining the dye; the only available commercial sample, supplied as tablets and specified to contain a certain amount of the dye, was found to have undergone considerable deterioration. Recourse was therefore taken to synthesise the dye.

Tillmans *et al.* (*Univ. Frankfurt a.m. Z. wnters Lebensm.*, 1928, 56, 272) prepared the indicator by coupling a solution of 2 : 6-dichloroquinone chlorimide with phenol in presence of aqueous alkali. This synthesis has been repeated under similar conditions by Gibbs *et al.* (U. S. Pub. Health Rep., 1929, suppl. No. 69, p. 35), Ven Hoo *et al.* (*Sci. Rep. Nat. Tsinghua Univ.*, 1934, 2A, 235) and Mikhailov (*Trans. Inst. Pure Chem. Reagents USSR.*, 1939, 17, 45). However, there is little published work detailing the exact conditions by which the synthesis of the dye could be carried out. The scheme used for its preparation in this laboratory may be represented as follows.

p-Nitrophenol is chlorinated with chlorate-chloride mixture to form 2 : 6-dichloro-(-nitrophenol (III) (Kollrep, *Annalen*, 1886, 234, 8). Alkaline hydrosulphite reduction of (III) gives the corresponding aminophenol (IV) in quantitative yield (Kollrep, *loc. cit.*) and the method is simpler and less time-consuming than the procedure of Mikhailov (*Trans. Inst. Pure Chem. Reagents USSR*, 1939, 16, 83) employing tin and hydrochloric acid. Addition of sodium hypochlorite solution to an alkaline solution of phenol, mixed with (IV), results in the formation of (I) in one stage and in about 80% yield. The synthesis of the dye in high yield is thus possible without isolation of the intermediate 2 : 6-dichloroquinone chlorimide, as reported by Gibbs (*loc. cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Chlorination of p-Nitrophenol.—*p*-Nitrophenol (22 g.) was dissolved in commercial hydrochloric acid (1000 c.c.). The solution was warmed and insoluble matter, if any, was filtered off. The solution was then poured in a filter-flask of about two litre capacity, fitted with a separating funnel containing the potassium chlorate solution (16 g. in 300 c.c. of water) and the side-tube attached to the water-pump for absorbing hydrochloric acid fumes. The potassium chlorate solution was gradually added with constant stirring to the reaction mixture during a period of about 20 minutes when the dichloro compound separated. The reaction liquid was then cooled in a refrigerator for some time and filtered. The product crystallised from water in the form of light yellow plates, m.p. 125°, yield 27 g. (76% of theory).

Reduction of 2 : 6-Dichloro-4-nitrophenol.—2 : 6-Dichloro-4-nitrophenol (25 g.) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (1250 c.c.) by heating to 80-90°. To the solution was gradually added sodium hydrosulphite (100 g.) during a period of about 20 minutes maintaining the temperature of the solution at 80°. The solution was kept alkaline throughout the reaction (tested intermittently with phenolphthalein paper for alkalinity and for hydrosulphite with vat paper). A change in colour of the original brown solution to a lighter shade indicated completion of the reaction. Excess of the sodium hydrosulphite was then destroyed by boiling the solution until it did not show any reaction with vat-paper. The solution was then allowed to attain the room temperature and acidified with just sufficient amount of acetic acid when a crystalline precipitate of the amine separated immediately. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from water as fine colourless needles turning gray on exposure to light, m.p. 165° (Kollrepp, *loc. cit.*, records the m.p. 165-66°). (Found : Cl, 39.8. $C_6H_5OCl_2N$ requires Cl, 40.0 per cent).

The amine being unstable was immediately used for the next reaction.

Condensation of 2 : 6-Dichloro-4-aminophenol with Phenol in presence of Sodium Hypochlorite and Formation of the Sodium 2 : 6-Dichloroindophenolate (I).— The sodium hypochlorite was prepared by passing chlorine in 10% sodium hydroxide solution, surrounded by ice-salt mixture (-10°) till saturated. The hypochlorite solution was found to contain 45 g. per litre of available chlorine and was freshly prepared every time.

2 : 6-Dichloro-4-aminophenol (9 g.) and phenol (72 g.) were taken in a flask, immersed in an ice-bath and sodium hypochlorite solution was gradually added to it with constant stirring. Soon lustrous, green, tiny needles of sodium 2 : 6-dichloroindophenolate began to separate. The solution was then allowed to stand in the refrigerator. The product was filtered and crystallised from brine (200 g. NaCl per litre) water. Second crystallisation (charcoal) improved the lustre of the product. The product was dried at 40° under vacuum, yield 10.3 g. (80% of theory). The dye was tested for its purity by standardisation against ascorbic acid according to the methods of Harris and Oliver (*Biochem. J.*, 1942, 36, 176) and Guerrant (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 25), and was found to have the same standard of purity as the commercial samples.

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